

Value chain analysis of turmeric subsector in Surkhet district of Nepal

*Ganesh Bhat Chhetri, Durga Devkota, Banita Sharma

Agriculture and Forestry University, Rampur, Chitwan, Nepal

*Corresponding email: ganeshkshetri31@gmail.com

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Original Research Article Received on Jan 11, 2020 Revised on Jan 24, 2020 Accepted on April Feb 06, 2020 Published on Feb 16, 2020</p> <p>Article Authors Ganesh Bhat Chhetri, Durga Devkota, Banita Sharma Corresponding Author Email ganeshkshetri31@gmail.com</p>	<p>A field experiment was carried out during the early summer seasons of 2018, at Turmeric (<i>Curcuma longa</i>) is a high value spice crop of high medicinal and economic concern (HVAP, 2011). It has been using in Ayurveda and medicinal propose from centuries which helps to boost up digestive system, circulatory system, nervous system and immune system (Gunnar, 2018). 60 household respondents were selected using simple random technique without replacement from Beriganga Municipality, Barahataal Village Municipality and Chaukune village Municipality. 4 co-operatives were selected from each level randomly and 5 respondent from each co-operatives, <i>i.e.</i> 20 respondents from each local level. 3 spice industries and 7 traders were selected purposively. Secondary data were collected from secondary sources like PMAMP, journal articles, MoAD etc. Descriptive statistics, benefit cost analysis, value chain analysis were carried out. The study reveals that 81.67% of populations were engaged in agriculture occupation as a primary source of income. The BC ratio of fresh, dry and powder turmeric was found to be 1.30, 1.09 and 1.36 (machinery), 1.16 (Dhiki Jhato) respectively. Similarly the cost of production of fresh dry and powder turmeric was found to be NRs. 18.46, NRs. 119.20 and NRs. 162.92 (machinery), NRs. 189.87 (Dhiki Jhato) respectively. Market margin of fresh, dry and powder turmeric was found to be NRs. 6.03, NRs. 25.07 and NRs. 179.70 respectively. In the study area major value chain actors were providers, producers, collectors, processors, wholesalers, retailers and consumers. Insufficient technical support and improved seed rhizome, insufficient price to cover cost of production and traders dominance in pricing were the major problems faced by turmeric producing community. This study suggests the farmers for seed production, value addition, marketing and distribution in farm level.</p>
<p>PUBLICATION INFO International Journal of Agricultural Invention (IJAI) RNI: UPENG/2016/70091 ISSN: 2456-1797 (P) Vol.: 5, Issue: 1, Pages: 16-24 Journal Homepage URL http://agriinventionjournal.com/ DOI: 10.46492/IJAI/2020.5.1.2</p>	<p>KEYWORDS Turmeric, Value, Subsector, Analysis, Surkhet District, Dhiki Jhato</p>

HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE

Chhetri, G. B., Devkota, D., Sharma, B. (2020) Value chain analysis of turmeric subsector in Surkhet district of Nepal, *International Journal of Agricultural Invention*, 5(1): 16-24. DOI: [10.46492/IJAI/2020.5.1.2](https://doi.org/10.46492/IJAI/2020.5.1.2)

Turmeric (*Curcuma longa*, Zingiberaceae) is a perennial, rhizomatous, herbaceous plant. It is one of the most important spice crops of Nepal. Among the high value crop, turmeric covers 11 % area and 15.07% in case of production (MoAD, 2018). Pseudo stem of turmeric are used as colouring and flavouring agent. Turmeric contains more than 300 naturally occurring components including beta-carotene, ascorbic acid, calcium, flavonoids, fiber, iron, niacin, potassium, zinc, and other nutrients but the chemical having high health benefit in turmeric is curcumin.

Curcumin are present in turmeric prevent heart disease, acts as antioxidant, improve depression and arthritis, anti-inflammatory and also reduce alzheimer and cancer (Gunnar, 2018). Fresh turmeric (Kapurkot 1) has 13.8% of powder formation ability, and 92.8% of dry turmeric is converted into powder. It contains 4.89% curcumin and 6.65% aromatic oils (PMAMP, 2017). Cucurminoids helps to reduce inflammation and reduce the possibility of heart attack of patients after surgery. It helps to controls knee pain from osteoarthritis also reduce skin irritation.

However, long term use may create gastrointestinal problems (NCCIH, 2018). India is the largest producer, consumer and exporter of turmeric in the world. It account for 80% of world turmeric production. Other major producers and exporters are Myanmar, Indonesia, Netherland, United Kingdom, Peru, Germany, China, France, and United State. India exported turmeric valued 182.53 million US dollar in 2017 (Conway, 2019). In fiscal year 2073/074, 43581 kg fresh (Rs 8511000), 36565 kg powder (Rs 591000) and 1287500 kg (NRs 15533700) slice or dry turmeric was imported while 139 kg (Rs 50000) fresh, 3290 Kg (NRs. 890000) powder and 25090.15 Kg slice or dry form of turmeric valued NRs. 7572000 was exported (MoAD, 2018). Study of value chain in turmeric subsector can play significant role in policy making and preparation, planning of new project work.

To provide the actual condition of small land holding farmers and to analyze linkage between stakeholders working in turmeric subsector, this study will be applicable. This research helps to investigate the evidence of value chain status of turmeric subsector in Surkhet district. This research helps to establish the linkage between stakeholders and service providers is the major challenge in series work to meet the demand and supply of value added product to maintain value chain governance. That enables the sustainable and balanced relation between the actors to maintain a favourable business environment. The major objective is to determine the actual need of production unit to consumption unit through the value chain approach by market information system for transfer of technology.

Methodology

In this section, research site selection, research design, sampling technique, sampling population, sampling size, sampling methods and data analysis techniques are studied.

Site Selection

On the basis of statistical analysis and review, Surkhet district was selected purposively in 2019 due to high potential of turmeric production, marketing channel and value addition process. To collect authentic data and minimize sampling error, 3 local level of Surkhet district was selected

according to their potential production accessibility of researcher, budget and time constraints and key informant interview with Mr. Padam Subedi (Agriculture officer at PMAMP zone implementation unit ginger/ turmeric) Bheriganga municipality, Barahataal village municipality and Chaukune village municipality were selected.

Preliminary Study

For the purpose of preliminary study, pilot survey was carried out to gather the statistical information of the target area. That information includes socioeconomic, demographic, topographic information about turmeric cultivation and marketing along with the relationship with stakeholders. This study was useful in the preparation of questionnaire. Sample size, sampling techniques and sampling procedures.

Farmers, village traders/middle man/ agent/ companies, and service providers were the focus of this research. 4 co- operatives were selected randomly in each local level and 5 farmers were randomly sampled through lottery system to make sample size 20 household in each local level. So the total sample size is 60 household. Similarly in 3 local level total 12 co-operatives were sampled for Key informant interview. 7 major traders were interviewed and data was taken and 2 major processing units/ companies were surveyed. Service provider Prime Minister Agriculture Modernization Project (PMAMP zone implementation unit Surkhet ginger/ turmeric) and High Value Agriculture Project in High hills and Mountains (HVAP) were selected purposively.

Methods and Technique of Data Collection

Primary Data

Semi structured questionnaire was developed for primary data purpose. Farmers are the major source of information. Turmeric farmers and their real problems were collected through household survey and KII for primary data.

Household Survey

60 households were randomly selected from 3 local levels and 4 co-operatives of each level through simple random sampling.

To know the current status of turmeric farmers and to share knowledge, information and perception questionnaire survey was conducted. Open ended and close ended questions were formed from where useful information was gathered.

Key Information Interview (KII)

The experienced personalities and expert in turmeric cultivating farmers were selected purposively. Zone officer, local leaders and presidents of co-operatives were the major key informants. Series of questions about the present scenario of turmeric production area, yield, productivity, number of farmers involved in turmeric cultivation and economic activities were asked.

Observation

Field visit and several observations were carried out in the production and marketing units including their problems, limitations, scope, constraints and opportunities.

Secondary Data

Secondary data were gathered from journals, relevant articles, newspapers, zone office, MOAD, krishi diary (AITC), HVAP, Ministry of Agriculture, internet etc. Production area, productivity, yield of different districts and trend analysis of Surkhet was carried out.

Data Analysis Method

The primary and secondary information collected from the field survey and other methods were analyzed by using Statistical Package of Social Science (SPSS) and Micro-Soft Excel for calculating benefit cost ratio, producers share, chain performance, value addition etc. at different stages of value chains. The primary and secondary information collected from field visit, questionnaire and KII were analyzed through Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) and Microsoft Excel for the calculation of benefit cost ratio, market margin, value chain performance, producers share etc. Both descriptive and analytical methods were used to analyze data. The outputs were represented through pie chart, regression line, timeline, bar diagram, and tables.

Economics of Production and Marketing System

Cost of Production

It is the total cost incurred in the production process including fixed cost and variable cost.

Fixed cost = Cost of land (NRs.) + Depreciation cost of farm equipment and machinery (NRs.) + Repair and maintenance cost (NRs.).

Cdeptec

Variable cost = Total cost of inputs + Total cost of labour

Where,

Input cost includes cost of seed, manure, packaging materials, transportation and communication and miscellaneous cost (NRs.). Labour cost includes cost of bullocks, field preparation FYM placement and planting, mulch collection, weeding, spraying, irrigation, harvesting, cleaning, grading, sorting, packaging, marketing and transportation (NRs.).

Gross Return

It is the total revenue after the quantity sold. Gross return = Quantity (Kg) * Price per unit (NRs.)

Benefit Cost Analysis

Gross return of production of turmeric and total cost for production were used to analyse the B/C ratio. Following formula is used to calculate B/C ratio:

$$\frac{B}{C} \text{ Ratio} = \frac{\text{Gross Return (Rs.)}}{\text{Total Cost (Rs.)}}$$

Where,

Gross return was calculated from the income of sold product (NRs.). The total cost of production was calculated by summation of variable cost and fixed cost incurred in the production process (NRs.).

If $\frac{B}{C} \text{ ratio} > 1$, project is feasible

If $\frac{B}{C} \text{ ratio} < 1$, project is infeasible

If $\frac{B}{C} \text{ ratio} = 1$, neutral

Market Margin

Market margin is the difference between the price purchases by consumer to the price received by producer.

Market margin = price of commodity – price received by farmer

$$Ps = \frac{Pp}{Pc} \times 100$$

Where,

Ps = producer's share

Pp = Producer's price

Pc = Price paid by consumer/retailer's price.

Producer's Share

Producer's share is the amount received by producer to the amount purchased by consumer. It is expressed in percentage.

Scaling Technique / Indexing

Problems related to production and marketing is ranked by using scaling technique/ indexing. These problems were categorized on the basis of severity of problems. The index was calculated by using following formula:

$$I = \frac{\sum Si \cdot fi}{n}$$

where,

Σ = Summation

I = Index (0<I<1)

Si = Scale value at *ith*

intensity fi = Frequency of *ith*

response n = Total no of respondents Σfi

1	0.8	0.6	0.4	0.2
↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Extremely Severe	Highly Severe	Severe	Moderately severe	Least Severe

Results and Discussion

Economic Analysis

Economic analysis of turmeric cultivation includes, cost of production, benefit cost ratio analysis of fresh, dried and powder form, value chain function and market margin.

Cost of Production

Cost of production in turmeric cultivation includes fixed cost and variable cost. Land rent, depreciation cost of machinery and repair maintenance cost are fixed cost whereas input cost, labour cost and other miscellaneous costs are included in variable cost. Cost of production of fresh turmeric was found to be NRs. 8200.30 per ropani. Among all cost, land rent occupy 6.09%, input cost occupy 54.51% and labour cost occupy 39.39%. Out of total cost, seed rhizome covers 31.37% and manure and FYM covers 16.36%.

While packaging, communication, land preparation, FYM placement and planning, mulch collection, weeding / irrigation, harvesting / grading/ cleaning / sorting, marketing and miscellaneous covers 0.3%, 0.16%, 6.63%, 10.22%, 10.36%, 0.96%, 9.95%, 1.24% and 6.24% of total cost of production.

Production of fresh turmeric was found to be 461.43 kg and average loss was found to be 17.14 Kg (3.71%) in one ropani of land. Production of 1 Kg fresh turmeric, Rs. 18.46 is incurred. Turmeric has various form of value addition. Githi and powder are the major value added form after cleaning, sorting and grading. To produce 1 Kg of githi, 5.18 Kg fresh turmeric is used. During githi production process, 2% handling and drying loss occurs. Rs. 119.20 was incurred to produce a Kg of githi.

Powder is the final value added form of turmeric in the consumption unit in Surkhet district. 90% of githi was converted into powder. By means of machinery, 1% loss of turmeric occurs during handling and packaging process. Rs. 162.92 was incurred to produce 1 Kg of turmeric powder by using machinery. 51.67% of total ho use hold were using machinery and 41.67% household were using traditional Dhiki Jhato technique in powder production process while remaining 6.66% household were not performing machinery and Dhiki Jhato. Dhiki Jhato is the traditional and conventional method used in the powder formation process. This method is labour inefficient. 1.5% handling and packaging loss was found from this technique. During the production of 1 Kg, Rs. 189.87 was incurred.

Table 1. Calculation of cost of production of fresh and dried turmeric

S.N.	Description	Quantity	Unit	Rate	Total
Cost of Production of Fresh Turmeric					
A	Land Rent	1	Ropani	500	500
B	Cost of Input				
1	Seed	106.42	Kg	24.17	2572.17
2	Manure/ FYM	25.4	Doko	52.83	1341.88
3	Packaging	1	Sack Lump sum		30.00
4	Communication	1	Lump sum		13.94
5	Miscellaneous	1	Lump sum		512.29
C	Cost of Labor				
1	Land preparation	0.48	Bullock day	1133.33	544.00
2	FYM placement and planting	1.48	Man day	566.67	838.67
3	Mulch collection	1.5	Man day	566.67	850.01
4	Weeding/spraying/irrigation	0.14	Man day	566.67	79.33
5	Harvesting/cleaning/sorting/grading/packing	1.44	Man day	566.67	816.00
6	Marketing/transportation	0.18	Lump sum	566.67	102.00
	Total production of fresh turmeric per ropani	461.43			
	Grand total cost for fresh turmeric per ropani				8200.30
	Loss in kg	17.14	3.71%		
	Production after loss (Kg)	444.29			
	Cost per kg of fresh turmeric (NRs.)				18.46

Table 2. Estimation of additional cost of dry formation

Additional Cost of Production of Dry Turmeric					
1	Boiling/ drying (444.29 Kg)	2.50	Man day	566.67	1416.67
2	Firewood and other equipment cost	1	Lump sum	400	400
	Total cost for drying				10016.97
	Total production of dry turmeric(Kg)	85.74			
	Loss in kg	1.71		(2%)	
	Net production after loss(Kg)	84.03			
	Cost per kg production of turmeric(NRs.)				119.20

Source: Field survey, 2019

Table 3. Estimation of additional cost of powder formation by machinery

Additional Cost of Production of Powder Turmeric Machinery (84.03 Kg)					
1	Machinery cost (51.67%)	84.03	Kg	20	1680.60
2	Packaging cost	1	Lump sum	500	500
	Grand total cost				12197.57
	Figures inside parentheses indicates percentage of household involved				
	Total production of powder turmeric	75.62			
	Loss in Kg	0.75 (1%)			
	Net production Kg	74.87			
	Cost per kg of turmeric production (NRs.)				162.92

Source; Field survey, 2019

Table 4. Estimation of additional cost of powder formation by Dhiki Jhato

Additional Cost of Production of Powder Turmeric Dhiki Jhato (84.03 Kg)					
1	Dhiki Jhato (41.67%)	6.4	Man day	566.67	3626.68
2	Packaging cost	1	Lump sum	500	500
	Grand total cost				14143.65
	Figures inside parentheses indicates percentage of household involved				
	Total production of powder turmeric kg	75.62			
	Loss in Kg	1.13 (1.5%)			
	Net production Kg	74.49			
	Cost per kg of turmeric production (NRs.)				189.87

Source: Field survey, 2019

Table 5. Estimation of BC ratio

S. N.	Particulars	Total Cost/ Ropani	Gross Revenue/ Ropani	B/C Ratio
1	Fresh	8200.30	10649.63	1.30
2	Githi	10016.97	10934.40	1.09
3	Powder			
a	Machinery	12197.57	16596.43	1.36
b	Dhiki Jhato	14143.65	16512.20	1.16

*Average price of fresh, dry and powder turmeric was Rs.23.97, Rs.130.12 and was Rs.221.67, Source: Field survey, 2019

Fig 1. Marketing Channel of turmeric in Surkhet

Table 6. Scaling of production problems

Production Problems	Index	Rank
Insufficient technical support	0.883217	1
Insufficient seed rhizome	0.87845	2
Poor quality seed	0.723533	3
Lack of appropriate training	0.551933	4
Poor irrigation facility	0.5138	5
Incidence of disease/pest	0.304067	6
Unavailable input	0.142	7

Table 7. Scaling of marketing problems

Marketing Problems	Index	Rank
Insufficient price to cover cost of production	0.953333	1
poor marketing infrastructure	0.913333	2
Traders dominance in pricing	0.813333	3
Inappropriate market information system	0.746667	4
No formal agreement with traders	0.206667	5

Table 8. SWOT analysis

Level	Internal Strength	Internal Weakness
Input	Requires relatively less investment for production Announcement of organic city (No use of inorganic compounds in turmeric) Relatively less requirement of irrigation Locally available mulching material, manure and human resources	Lack of improved varieties Less priority of government No application of fertiliser Traditional farming practices Lack of appropriate training No research activities
Production	Availability of local resistance variety against disease pest High content of curcumin in locally cultivate landraces Availability of marginal land for turmeric cultivation Traditional cultivation practices, indigenous technology and knowledge Technical support from government and non-government organisation (HVAP, zone implementation unit etc.) Transfer of technology in production unit	Low productivity Lack of appropriate transfer of technology No cropping plan No adoption of commercial farming
Output	Relatively long shelf life Daily consumption in household Spice crop and also has high medicinal value Pharmaceuticals, cosmetics and industrial use Low postharvest and handling loss High B/C ratio	Traders dominance in price determination Poor market information system Unknown actual market demand and supply Improper marketing infrastructure Lack of co-ordination with service providers Lack of linkage between stakeholders Communication gap between producers and processor
Level	External Opportunity	External Threat
Input	Research activities and varietal improvement programme Increasing number of service providers Subsidy provision for small farmers and commercial farmers	Degradation of landraces and local varieties
Production	Employment opportunity Eco-friendly Cover crop Reduce soil erosion	Emergence of new disease and pest
Output	Export potential Import substitution Value addition High demand from industries, companies and pharmaceuticals	Trade depended on India market Forest degradation and lack of mulching materials

Benefit Cost Ratio

Turmeric has different value added form *i.e.* githi, powder etc. In one ropani area, B/C ratio was found to be 1.30 of fresh turmeric, 1.09 of githi, 1.36 of powder formed by machinery and 1.16 of powder formed by Dhiki Jhato

Distribution of Cost and Margin

Table number 10 illustrates the marketing margin of different value added forms of turmeric and linkage with value chain actors. Field study

reveals that, cost of production of per kg fresh turmeric was NRs. 18.46 including 3.71% post-harvest loss. Farm gate price of fresh turmeric was NRs. 23.97/kg with profit margin NRs. 5.41/kg. To produce 1kg dry turmeric NRs. 119.20 is incurred including 2% loss in farmer's field. They sold dry turmeric at price NRs. 129.93/kg at farm gate. By using machinery farmer produce turmeric powder at NRs. 162.92/kg however per kg cost reaches NRS. 189.87 including 1% and 1.5% handling losses and sold to consumer at price NRs. 220.30/kg respectively.

From the social survey the market margin of fresh, dry and powder turmeric was found to be NRs. 6.03/kg, NRs. 25.07/kg and NRs. 179.70/kg respectively.

Value Share of Turmeric

Field survey, 2019 reveals that the 48.36% of total production was sold by producer and 25.38% was utilised for household consumption and powder formation while 23.06% was stored for seed purpose and remaining 3.71% was lost during value addition. Site visit and survey shows that, out of total sold fresh turmeric 25.01% of was sold to groups or co-operatives, 45.71% was sold to local trader 29.26% was sold to other companies, and middle man/ agents.

Farmers are performing value addition activity in case of turmeric commodity by cleaning, sorting, grading, slicing, boiling, drying and grinding. Some farmers were selling dry slices and githis. Only few farmers sell dry turmeric. Maximum amount was sold to traders and some proportion was sold to co-operatives and groups. Generally, small medium farmers process their dry turmeric to powder form in local level. Excess of turmeric, they sold to the different consumers. About 77.65% was sold directly to consumer, 11.64% was sold to neighbours and remaining 10.70% was sold to middleman/traders.

Problem Ranking

In Surkhet, there were several problems related to turmeric production and marketing. Indexing/scaling technique was employed to prioritise the problems. This method was implemented and explained below.

SWOT Analysis

SWOT analysis provides knowledge about strength and opportunities in production and marketing of turmeric subsector and also informs weakness and risk that helps in preparation and planning of business enterprise. Gathered information from FGD, KII and field survey, following situation was analyzed.

Conclusion

Input providers, farmers, local collectors, co-operatives, traders, processors, wholesalers, retailers, exporters and consumers were major factors involved. Farming technique should be changed into commercial and promote improved cultivation technique for low cost of production, high production and productivity. To fulfill water demand, irrigation facility should be provided and further research should be conducted in effect and use of different organic and inorganic (plastic) mulching materials. Market information should be provided to different actors involved in chain activity in time to maintain market in equilibrium. Farmers should perform value addition and marketing through group/co-operatives.

Suggestions and Recommendations

- Based on the relevant, fact and findings, the following suggestions and recommendations were made on the research related to value chain analysis of turmeric subsector in Surkhet district which could be useful in policy making, project planning and further research in related studies. This could be useful to actors, stakeholders and facilitators to provide market information and to maintain equilibrium in demand and supply in domestic, national, and international market.
- Poor management system, traditional/conventional cultivation practices and subsistence farming system causing low production, productivity and high labor cost. Farming technique should be changed into commercial and improved cultivation technique for low cost of production, high production and productivity, ultimately maximum profit can be achieved.
- Climate change, irregular rainfall, insufficient irrigation and poor mulching system (unavailable required mulching material) creating low water supply that reduces yield. To fulfill water demand irrigation facility should provide and further research should be conducted in effect and use of different organic and inorganic (plastic) mulching materials.
- Market information should be provided to different actors involved in chain activity in time to maintain market in equilibrium.

- PMAMP zone should invest fund in the field of organic manure production and marketing *i.e.* vermin-composting, managing the street live stocks, composting of decayed fruits and vegetables of Haat bazar *etc.*
- Government should intervene to fix floor price to cover the cost of production.
- Medicinal and chemical property of turmeric should be explored for the establishment of pharmaceuticals and ayurvedic institutions.
- Farmers should go through groups and co-operatives in production, value addition, marketing and distribution of products to minimize the dominance of traders.
- Trainings in adoption of new technology, cultivation practices, post-harvest handling processing and storage should be provided.

References

- AITC (2019) Kirshi diary, Kathamandu: Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock Development.
- CBS (2012) Statistical Year Book 2011/12, Kathamandu, Nepal: Government of Nepal National Planning Commission Secretariat Central Bureau of Statistics.
- CBS (2017) Village Municipality and Municipality profile of Surkhet District 2074, Birendranagar, Surkhet: Government of Nepal, National Planning Commission, Central Bureau of Statistics.
- Conway, J. (2019) <https://www.statista.com/statistics>, retrieved from [www.statista.com:https://www.statista.com/statistics/798287/main-turmeric-export-countries-worldwide](https://www.statista.com/statistics/798287/main-turmeric-export-countries-worldwide).
- Gunnar, K. (2018) www.healthline.com/nutrition, retrieved from [www.healthline.com: https://www.healthline.com/nutrition/top-10-evidence-based-health-benefits-of-turmeric](https://www.healthline.com/nutrition/top-10-evidence-based-health-benefits-of-turmeric).
- HVAP (2011) Value Chain of Turmeric, Birendranagar, Surkhet, Nepal: Government of Nepal, Ministry of Agriculture Development.
- MOAD (2011) Stastical Information on Nepalese Agriculture, 2010/11, Kathamandu, Nepal: Agrubusiness Promotion and Statistics Division.
- MOAD (2012) Stastical Information on Nepalese Agriculture, 2010/11, Kathamandu, Nepal: Agrubusiness Promotion and Statistics Division.
- MOAD (2012) Statistical Information on Nepalese Agriculture, 2011/12, Kathamandu, Nepal: Agriculture Promotion and Statistical Division.
- MOAD (2018) Statistical Information on Nepalese Agriculture, 2073/74 (2016/17) Kathamandu, Nepal: Ministry of Agriculture, Land Managment and Cooperatives, Government of Nepal.
- NARC (2014) Cultivation of ginger and turmeric, Kapurkot, Salyan: Ministry of Agriculture, Government of Nepal.
- NCCIH (2018) Turmeric, Unites State: NCCIH Publication, D-367.
- PMAMP (2017) Zone Profile, Birendranagar, Surkhet, Nepal: Ministry of Agriculture, Land managment and co-operatives, Government of Nepal.
- Timilsina, K., Shrestha, K., Chapaigh, T. and Pandey, S. (2011) Value chain alanalysis of turmeric (*Curcuma longa*) in Estern Nepal, *Nepal Agriculture Research Journal*, Vol-11.